

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation – User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Experimental analysis and simulation of a solar-driven polygeneration system associated with molten salt and water storage
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	SolarMS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS, Cyprus
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Solar energy, concentrated solar power, Rankine cycle, molten salt storage
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	25 May 2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	2 June 2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	26 May 2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	2 June 2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	3 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	25 May for traveling. On 27 May and 28 May, the RI was not used because these were weekend days, which were non-working days. On 30 May, the RI was not used due to the summer school schedule during almost all of that day
Number of days using the RI	5 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The main objectives of this project, which is taking place during my Ph.D. studies are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visiting the high-level research infrastructure of PROTEAS in Cyprus. • Observing in real-time the performance of this facility. • Taking real experience in the operation of energy systems, that are simulated during my Ph.D. studies, such as a solar collectors' field, a thermal energy storage tank, and a Rankine cycle. 	

- Receiving and processing experimental data, which includes many measured parameters and values, such as temperature values, flow rates, and pressure values.
- Simulation studies about the systems integrated at the PROTEAS facility.
- Validation of the proposed simulation models through the experimental data.
- Contact and interaction with experts and other scientists that are working in similar scientific fields.
- Writing a scientific paper to disseminate the results.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The purpose of my trip to Cyprus was to work at the PROTEAS research infrastructure and the Cyprus Institute. PROTEAS is one of the few research facilities in Europe that include different renewable energy systems and storage technologies. More specifically, it consists of photovoltaic panels, a wind turbine, two solar Stirling engines, batteries, a heliostat field associated with a central receiver, a molten salt storage tank, a Rankine cycle, and desalination units. On the other hand, the Cyprus Institute is a research, innovation, and education institution, located in Nicosia, Cyprus, which owns and supervises the PROTEAS facility.

My work was mainly focused on the concentrated solar power (CSP) plant, which included a heliostat field associated with a central receiver, a molten salt storage tank, and a Rankine cycle. These technologies are strongly related to my Ph.D. research, and scope, which is the investigation and analysis of thermal energy storage systems, as well as the possible hybridization with other storage technologies, in solar power plants, and buildings.

First, I visited all the systems which were integrated into that facility, and also the main building of the facility, which included the receiver, the storage tank, the Rankine cycle, and the control room. During that visit, I had the opportunity to observe and understand the performance of a CSP plant in real-time conditions. The staff explained to me how the implemented systems were working and interacted with each other during the daily operation. Additionally, I watched how the staff was dealing with problems that arose during the operation. That research experience was not possible in my home organization.

At all the examined units, which were the central receiver, the molten salt storage tank, and the Rankine cycle, there were many measurement devices, such as thermocouples for temperature measurement, flow meters for flow rate measurement, manometers for pressure measurement, and electrical power meters. More specifically, there were many thermocouples at the core and the external surface of both the receiver and the tank. Moreover, thermocouples, manometers, and flow meters were installed at the molten salt loop, which connected the receiver and the tank, as well as at the Rankine cycle. In parallel, there were electric power meters at the pump motors and the generator. At the PROTEAS, a meteorological station was also placed to measure the locally available solar irradiation and the ambient temperature. All those quantities were monitored in the control room of the facility. Historical data regarding the aforementioned quantities for many years of operation were available in the control room database.

From that database, I received experimental data about the performance of the central receiver and the molten salt storage tank. That data came from the days in recent months when the molten salt loop and the receiver were operated. In addition, I received historical data about the Rankine cycle operation and the desalination units. The molten salt loop, the receiver, as well as the steam loop, which was connected to the Rankine cycle, were not operated continuously.

Based on the received experimental data, I performed data processing, and I defined the performance curves of the central receiver with acceptable accuracy. That procedure was the basis of simulation studies. During the simulation studies, the developed models about the receiver, and

the thermal energy storage tank will be validated through the experimental data. Finally, the Rankine cycle and the desalination units will be modeled.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Mathematical background

First, the main parameters of the investigated heliostat field associated with a central receiver at the PROTEAS facility are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Main information and parameters of the heliostat field and the receiver [1].

Parameter	Value
Number of heliostats	50
Tower height	14 m
Heliostat area	5 m ²
Receiver storage tank volume	1.81 m ³
Receiver front aperture diameter	0.8 m
Geometrical concentration ratio	497

The initial work includes the data processing of the experimental measurements from the receiver, and the molten salt loop as well as the irradiation and ambient temperature data from the meteorological station. Except for temperature and flow rate data about the molten salt, the available thermal load on the receiver is calculated continuously during the facility operation, considering all the optical losses in the heliostat field and the receiver. More specifically, the reflection losses in both the heliostats and the receiver, the cosine losses, the absorptivity of the heliostats, the shading losses, the blocking losses, the atmospheric attenuation losses, as well as the spillage losses are taken into account [2,3]. The used software is Tonatiuh++, based on the Monte Carlo Ray Tracing method [4]. The ratio of the available thermal load on the receiver (Q_{avail}) to the available solar irradiation load (Q_{solar}) is defined as:

$$K = \frac{Q_{avail}}{Q_{solar}} \quad (1)$$

The ratio (K) is also considered the theoretical optical efficiency of the system. A common strategy in solar thermal systems is the definition of the incident angle modifier, which can be described as a function of the incident angle [5]. However, in a heliostat field, each heliostat has a different solar incident angle. To make a common definition for the entire solar field, the incident angle can be approximated by the solar zenith angle (θ_z), which is the angle between the sun's rays and the vertical direction [6]. This approach is also illustrated in Figure 1. So, it is decided, similarly to the incident angle modifier, to describe the theoretical optical efficiency (K) as a function of the solar zenith angle by the following expression:

$$K(\theta_z) = a + b \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta_z)} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

The solar zenith angle can be calculated through the solar altitude angle (α) as [2]:

$$\theta_z = 90^\circ - \alpha \quad (3)$$

The solar altitude angle (α) can be defined as [2]:

$$\sin(\alpha) = \sin(L) \cdot \sin(\delta) + \cos(L) \cdot \cos(\delta) \cdot \cos(h_s) \quad (4)$$

In Equation 4, (L) is the local latitude angle (34.71° N at the PROTEAS facility), and (δ) is the solar declination angle that is described in degrees as below [2]:

$$\delta = 23.45^\circ \cdot \sin\left(\frac{360^\circ(284+n)}{365}\right) \quad (5)$$

(n) is the day number, for example for January 1, $n=1$. Additionally, (h_s) is the hour angle in degrees calculated as [2]:

$$h_s = \frac{[\text{min from local solar noon}]}{4 \frac{\text{min}}{\text{deg}}} \quad (6)$$

The local solar time in minutes, which is different from the local clock time, is determined as [2]:

$$[\text{local solar time}] = [\text{local clock time}] + ET - 4 \cdot (l_{st} - l_{local}) \quad (7)$$

- (ET) is the equation of time in minutes that is defined as [2]:

$$ET = 9.87 \cdot \sin(2B) - 7.53 \cdot \cos(B) - 1.5 \cdot \sin(B) \quad (8)$$

- (B) is calculated in degrees as [2]:

$$B = \frac{360(n-81)}{364} \quad (9)$$

- (l_{st}) is the local clock time meridian in degrees (30° E at the PROTEAS facility)
- (l_{local}) is the local longitude in degrees (33.26° E at the PROTEAS facility)

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the heliostat field and the central receiver.

The available solar irradiation is defined as:

$$Q_{\text{solar}} = n_{\text{hel}} \cdot A \cdot G \quad (10)$$

(G) is the direct normal irradiation (DNI), (n_{hel}) the number of heliostats, which is equal to 50, when all the heliostats are in service, and (A) the aperture area of each heliostat, which is equal to 5 m² (the heliostats are of square shape with a length of 2.25 m each). The useful heat of the system (Q_u), which is captured by the molten salt (60% NaNO₃ - 40% KNO₃) through the receiver, is described by the following expression:

$$Q_u = m \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{r,\text{out}} - T_{r,\text{in}}) \quad (11)$$

(m) is the mass flow rate, (c_p) is the molten salt specific heat capacity, which is assumed at 1.5 kJ/kgK [2], ($T_{r,\text{in}}$) and ($T_{r,\text{out}}$) are the temperature values at the receiver inlet and outlet, respectively. The overall thermal efficiency of the system is determined by the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{th}} = \frac{Q_u}{Q_{\text{solar}}} \quad (12)$$

According to the literature, thermal efficiency can be described as a polynomial expression of the theoretical optical efficiency (K), and the quantity: $\left(\frac{T_{r,\text{in}} - T_{\text{amb}}}{G}\right)$, where (T_{amb}) is the ambient temperature, as [7]:

$$\eta_{\text{th}} = c_1 \cdot K(\theta_z) + c_2 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{r,\text{in}} - T_{\text{amb}}}{G}\right) \quad (13)$$

Results

The received data come from the facility operation from January to April 2023. To evaluate the data, all the measured parameters, such as temperatures, and flow rates, are weighted per 10 minutes, calculating the average values. Thus, numerous operating points are defined. From all these operating points during this period, operating points from quite sunny days and hours when large solar irradiation values are achieved, are selected to be examined. At these operating points, direct normal irradiation values from 830 to 920 W/m² and molten salt temperature values in the receiver from 370-480°C, have been measured.

In Figure 2, the calculated theoretical optical efficiency (K) depending on the quantity: $\left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta_z)} - 1\right)$ is illustrated. It is obvious that there is a linear correlation between the two variables, and the coefficients of Equation 1 can be defined. So, the parameter (K) can be described with respect to the solar zenith angle by the following expression:

$$K(\theta_z) = 0.8868 - 0.3373 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta_z)} - 1\right) \quad (14)$$

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is equal to 77.91%, which is considered an acceptable value. Moreover, according to Figure 3, the overall thermal efficiency seems to have a linear decreasing rate when the quantity: $\left(\frac{T_{r,in}-T_{amb}}{G}\right)$ increases. This correlation is a reasonable one according to the literature [7]. Taking into account the calculated values of the overall thermal efficiency and the quantity: $\left(\frac{T_{r,in}-T_{amb}}{G}\right)$, as well as the theoretical optical efficiency (K), as defined by Equation 14, a linear regression is carried out to define the coefficients of Equation 13. So, Equation 13 is modified as:

$$\eta_{th} = 0.6608 \cdot K(\theta_z) - 0.0205 \cdot \left(\frac{T_{r,in}-T_{amb}}{G}\right) \quad (15)$$

The first coefficient, which is equal to 0.6608 regards the reduction that must be applied to the theoretical optical efficiency to define the optical efficiency in real-time conditions. The second one, which is equal to 0.0205, is the linear thermal loss coefficient to approximate the thermal losses according to the experimental results. The comparative results between the thermal efficiency values calculated by the experimental data, and the corresponding values calculated by the linear correlation above, are presented in Figure 4. The mean deviation between the experimental and the approximate results is 2.43%. Additionally, the coefficient of determination (R^2) of Equation 15 is found at 76.30%. So, this linear approximation is accurate and valid enough to perform simulation studies.

Figure 2: Theoretical optical efficiency (K) depending on the quantity: $\left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta_z)} - 1\right)$.

Figure 3: Overall thermal efficiency (η_{th}) depending on the quantity: $\left(\frac{T_{r,in} - T_{amb}}{G}\right)$.

Figure 4: Comparative results of the overall thermal efficiency calculated by the experimental data, and the linear approximation.

References

- [1] E.V. Votyakov, M.C. Georgiou, E. Guillen, E. Stiliaris, C.N. Papanicolas, Experimental methodology to calculate thermal losses of a molten salt cavity receiver, AIP Conference Proceedings 2033, 040041 (2018).

[2] Goswami Y. (2015). Principles of solar engineering, 3rd edition, CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, Florida, USA.

[3] P. Schöttl, G. Bern, D. W. van Rooyen, J. Flesch, T. Fluri, P. Nitz, Efficient modeling of variable solar flux distribution on Solar Tower receivers by interpolation of few discrete representations, Solar Energy 160 (2018) 43–55.

[4] E.V. Votyakov, C.N. Papanicolas, Consistent multiphysics simulation of a central tower CSP plant as applied to ISTORE, AIP Conference Proceedings 1850, 160027 (2017).

[5] C. Rasmussen, L. Frölke, P. Bacher, H. Madsen, C. Rode, Semi-parametric modelling of sun position dependent solar gain using Bsplines in grey-box models, Solar Energy 195 (2020) 249–258.

[6] E. Bellos, C. Tzivanidis, Development of analytical expressions for the incident angle modifiers of a linear Fresnel reflector, Solar Energy 173 (2018) 769-779.

[7] J. Blanco, D. Alarcón, B. Sánchez, S. Malato, M.I. Maldonado, Technical comparison of different solar-assisted heat supply systems for a multi-effect seawater distillation unit, ISES Solar ISES SolarWorld Congress 2003 Göteborg, Sweden, 2003.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The main conclusions of the initial work and results are described below:

- Sunny days and hours are the most proper periods to investigate and analyze the performance of the heliostat field coupled with a central tower receiver.
- A correlation between the theoretical optical efficiency and the solar zenith angle is assumed. The linear regression between the theoretical optical efficiency (K) and the quantity: $\left(\frac{1}{\cos(\theta_z)} - 1\right)$ leads to a linear correlation, with a coefficient of determination (R²) equal to 77.91%.
- The overall thermal efficiency is considered a linear function of the theoretical optical efficiency and the quantity: $\left(\frac{T_{r,in} - T_{amb}}{G}\right)$. This approach is confirmed as the defined polynomial achieves a coefficient of determination (R²) at 76.30%.
- The linear approximation equations of both the theoretical optical efficiency and the overall thermal efficiency are valid enough to perform further simulation activities.
- These correlations will be used in order to simulate the receiver, the thermal energy storage tank, and the entire molten salt loop on a daily basis.
- The results of the daily simulation studies will be validated with the experimental data.
- The produced solar heat feeds a Rankine cycle, and desalination units at the facility. These units will be also simulated properly.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

During my stay in Cyprus, I had the opportunity to work at the PROTEAS research infrastructure and the Cyprus Institute. First, I visited the PROTEAS facility, which was a research facility that included different renewable energy and storage technologies. That installation was made up of photovoltaic panels, a wind turbine, two solar Stirling engines, batteries, a concentrated solar power (CSP) plant, and desalination units. From my side, I concentrated on the CSP plant, which included a heliostat field associated with a central receiver, a molten salt storage tank, and a Rankine cycle, as those technologies were related to my Ph.D. research. So, I observed and experienced the performance of a solar energy plant in real-time conditions, which was not possible in my home organization. Additionally, I received experimental data about the performance of the aforementioned systems. Then, I defined the performance curves of the central receiver, that will be used in the following simulation/modeling studies. Finally, these models will be validated according to the experimental data.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The problems and the issues during the TNA related work are:

- 1) The heating and cooling units that were mentioned in the application form are not currently installed at the PROTEAS facility. These units will probably install in the future to convert the current installation into a polygeneration plant that will provide useful heating to a district heating network or cooling. So, there are no available experimental data for such units.
- 2) The implementation of the water storage is a future action of the facility and is not currently available. So, there are no available experimental data for this kind of system. Currently, there is a storage tank for seawater that is useful for the desalination process and the cooling of the water/steam at the Rankine cycle.

Intended publications

The final purpose of this project is to publish a scientific paper in a journal, written by the user, in cooperation with the PROTEAS and the Cyprus Institute staff. This paper can be further disseminated via LinkedIn, and ResearchGate into a broad community of researchers.

Data management

The data which has been provided by the PROTEAS and the Cyprus Institute, are confidential. So, the processing of the data and publication of respective results are conducted with the consent of the staff of the PROTEAS and the Cyprus Institute.

Conclusions / additional comments

I would like to thank the StoRIES coordination team, as well as the Cyprus Institute and the PROTEAS facility staff for their support and the opportunity to work together.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RisurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
In my opinion, the RI can be upgraded. For example, it should work more days per week to increase its productivity and impact. Additionally, this facility can provide heat to a local destoring heating network.					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Some energy storage technologies are not represented at all or are represented less than others. So, facilities with pumped hydro energy storage, ammonia production, and storage units as well as concentrated solar plants coupled with novel heat transfer and storage fluids such as supercritical carbon dioxide, can be added.					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
I would like to suggest that in the future the TNA should be combined with new installations in the research infrastructures. That's why, the researchers will work on the design and preparation of new installations, not only on existing ones. Additionally, TNA should be applied to industrial projects, to increase the commercialization of energy storage technologies.					

Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have not taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support.					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.